

Resonance Dynamics in a Double-Well Parametric Quintic Oscillator: Probing Well Depth and Location Dependencies

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This study explores the influence of the depth and location of minima of a double-well potential on vibrational resonance in a parametric quintic oscillator. The system experiences dual driving forces—a low-frequency component, $(f \cos \omega t)$, and a high-frequency component, $(g \cos \Omega t)$. The response of the system manifests in two distinct motions: a slow motion characterized by the frequency ω and a fast motion characterized by the frequency Ω . Utilizing the flow equation approach, we analytically derive the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ from the equation governing the system's slow motion. By employing an approximate theoretical expression for $a_0(\omega)$ at low frequencies (ω), we investigate the impact of the depth and location of minima of the double-well potential on vibrational resonance. Modulating the amplitude of the high-frequency force g allows control over the number of resonances based on the depth and location of the wells. Adjusting system parameters through the manipulation of well depth and location enables the achievement of optimal vibrational resonance. Moreover, the alterations induced by these two parameters in the parametrically driven system are found to be more extensive than those observed in the original system. The theoretical results are validated through numerical simulations.

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1. Introduction

Parametric excitation and double-well potentials have been extensively utilized to amplify or detect weak signals [1]. These fundamental physical concepts, observed across various scientific fields, form the basis of the phenomenon of Vibrational Resonance (VR) [2]. Introduced analogously to the well-known stochastic resonance (SR) [3], VR has gained prominence in the realm of nonlinear dynamics over the past two decades. The prevailing paradigm for all proposed and studied models involves the response of nonlinear systems to two distinct driving forces—one with a slower frequency and the other with a frequency

much faster than the former [4-20]. VR in parametrically excited nonlinear systems is manifested when the system's parameters undergo periodic modulation. This modulation introduces a time-dependent aspect to the system, and if the modulation frequency matches a natural frequency of the system, resonance can occur. In such cases, the system amplifies its response, displaying enhanced vibrations or oscillations. Parametric excitation is a common occurrence in various physical systems, such as pendulums or electronic circuits, where external influences periodically alter system parameters, leading to VR phenomena. In recent years, considerable interest has been devoted to the study of the combined effect of parametric excitation and dual-frequency forces [21-27]. Notably, Anisha Nashrin *et al.* [28] explored

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the occurrence of VR in a parametrically driven quintic oscillator with five different forms of double-well potentials. In this paper, we investigate the role of the depth of the potential wells and the distance between the location of a minimum and local maximum of the symmetric double-well potential on vibrational resonance in a parametric quintic oscillator. Importantly, this objective can be achieved through a theoretical approach. The primary motivation of this work is to precisely investigate the influence of the depth and location of the double-well potential on the Vibrational Resonance (VR) phenomenon in a parametrically excited quintic oscillator. Additionally, this paper aims to introduce a periodic variation in the natural frequency of the oscillator, coinciding with both the lower forcing frequency and the parametric forcing frequency.

The structure of the rest of the paper is as follows: In Section 2, the model is presented. Section 3 provides a detailed analytical description of the resonance behavior. The impact of the depth of wells on VR is discussed in Section 4, while Section 5 delves into the influence of the location of minima of the potential wells on VR. Finally, Section 6 offers a concise conclusion.

2. The model

The equation of motion for the damped parametric quintic oscillator subjected to two periodic forces can be expressed as follows:

$$\ddot{x} + d\dot{x} - A\omega_0^2(1 + q \cos \omega_p t)x + B\beta x^3 + C\gamma x^5 = f \cos \omega t + g \cos \Omega t, \quad (1)$$

where $\Omega \gg \omega$ and the potential of the system in the absence of damping, parametric excitation and external forces is given by:

$$V(x) = -\frac{1}{2} A\omega_0^2 x^2 + \frac{1}{4} B\beta x^4 + \frac{1}{6} C\gamma x^6, \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (1), the term $f \cos \omega t$ denotes the lower frequency drive, while $g \cos \Omega t$ represents the high-frequency drive. Parametric excitation is introduced through the term $q \cos \omega_p t$, with q as

the amplitude of the parametric excitation, and the magnitude of the parametric frequency chosen to be $\omega = \omega_p$. For $\omega_0^2 > 0$, $\beta, \gamma, A, B, C > 0$, the potential $V(x)$ takes the form of a symmetric double-well. In the range $-1 < q < 1$, the system exhibits a bistable oscillator in unstable equilibrium on the crest of a double-well potential, oscillating about a stable equilibrium. This potential, $V(x)$, is commonly employed to model optical stability in dispersive media, where the refractive index depends on optical intensity [29]. Furthermore, Eq.(1) serves as a model for a magneto-elastic beam exposed to a nonuniform distribution of permanent magnets in the absence of external periodic forces and parametric excitation [30].

When $\omega_0^2 = 1$, $\beta = 1$, $\gamma = 1$ and $A = B = C = 1$ there are equilibrium points at $(0,0)$ and $(\pm\sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}}, 0)$. At $(0,0)$, $\lambda = \pm 1$, so this point is a saddle. At $(\pm\sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}}, 0)$, $\lambda \simeq \pm 0.935i$, so this points are centers. When $A = B = C = \alpha_1$, potential has a local maximum at $x_1^* = 0$ and two

minima at $x_{2,3}^* = \pm\sqrt{\frac{-\beta + \sqrt{\beta^2 - 4\gamma\omega_0^2}}{2\gamma}}$ and

two maxima at $x_{4,5}^* = \pm\sqrt{\frac{-\beta - \sqrt{\beta^2 - 4\gamma\omega_0^2}}{2\gamma}}$.

The depths of the left- and right-wells denoted by D_L and D_R respectively are same and equal to $\alpha_1[6\omega_0^2 p + 3\beta p^2 + 2\gamma p^3]/12$, where $p = \frac{-\beta + \sqrt{\beta^2 - 4\gamma\omega_0^2}}{2\gamma}$. By varying the parameter α_1

the depths of the two wells can be varied keeping the values of x_1^* and $x_{2,3}^*$ are kept constant. The

system with $A = \frac{1}{\alpha_2^2}$, $B = \frac{1}{\alpha_2^4}$ and $C = \frac{1}{\alpha_2^6}$ with

$\alpha_2 \neq 0$, the minima of $V(x)$ are $x_1^* = 0$, $x_{2,3}^* = \pm\alpha_2\sqrt{\frac{-\beta + \sqrt{\beta^2 - 4\gamma\omega_0^2}}{2\gamma}}$ and the maxima are

$x_{4,5}^* = \pm\alpha_2\sqrt{\frac{-\beta - \sqrt{\beta^2 - 4\gamma\omega_0^2}}{2\gamma}}$ and in this

case, $D_L = D_R = [6\omega_0^2 p + 3\beta p^2 + 2\gamma p^3]/12$ is independent of α_2 . Thus, by varying α_2 the depth of the wells of $V(x)$ can be kept constant while

FIG. 1. Shape of the potential $V(x)$ for $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0$ and (a) $A = B = C = \alpha_1$ and (b) $A = \frac{1}{\alpha_2}, B = \frac{1}{\alpha_2}, C = \frac{1}{\alpha_2}$. In the subplots, the values of α_1 and α_2 for continuous line, dashed line and painted circles are 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5, respectively.

FIG. 2. Response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_1 with (a) $\Omega = 12$ and $\Omega = 15$. Labels (i)–(iii) correspond to $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0$ and 2.0 respectively. The theoretical and numerical values of $a_0(\omega)$ are represented by continuous lines and painted circles. The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, q = 0.1, f = 0.05$ and $\omega = \omega_p = 1.0$.

the distance between the local maximum and the minima can be changed. Figures (1(a)) and (1(b)) illustrate the effect of α_1 and α_2 . For convenience,

the system (1) with $A = B = C = \alpha_1$ and $A = \frac{1}{\alpha_2}, B = \frac{1}{\alpha_2}, C = \frac{1}{\alpha_2}$ are represented by PS1 and PS2 respectively. Rajasekar *et al.* [31]

FIG. 3. Response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_1 with (a) $\omega = \omega_p = 1.5$ and (b) $\omega = \omega_p = 2.0$. Labels (i)-(iii) correspond to $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0$ and 2.0 respectively. The theoretical and numerical values of $a_0(\omega)$ are represented by continuous lines and painted circles. The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, q = 0.1, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

analyzed the role of the depth and location of minima of a double-well potential on VR in both overdamped and underdamped Duffing oscillator systems. Arathi *et al.* [32] studied the impact of the depth of the wells and multifractal analysis on stochastic resonance in a triple-well system. Ravisankar *et al.* [33] investigated the effect of depth and location of minima of a double-well potential on VR in a linearly damped quintic oscillator. Recently, Chen *et al.* [34] studied the impact of depth and location of the wells on VR in a triple-well system. In the present work, we consider the system (1) with arbitrary α_1 and α_2 at which resonance occurs, and we analyze the effect of the depth of the wells and the distance between the location of a minimum and a local maximum of the potential $V(x)$ on vibrational resonance.

3. Theoretical approach

3.1. Effective frequency and effective potential

In this section, we employ the method of direct separation of motions, as described by Blekhman [13], recognized as an effective formulation of vibrational mechanics. This method allows us to derive the equation of motion for the slow motion, modulated by parameters of the fast driving signal analytically. Assuming that for a long time $\Omega \gg \omega$ and introducing $\tau = \Omega t$, we consider the solution of Eq. (1) as the sum of a slow motion $s(t)$ with a period of $2\pi/\omega$ and a fast motion $\psi(t, \Omega t)$ with a period of $2\pi/\Omega$ (or a period of 2π in the fast time $\tau = \Omega t$), i.e., $x = s(t) + \psi(t, \tau)$. The mean value with respect to the fast time τ is given by

$$\langle \psi(t, \tau) \rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \psi(t, \tau) d\tau = 0. \quad (3)$$

The goal is to obtain two systems of integral-differential equations from Eq.(1) such that a pair

FIG. 4. The theoretical response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_1 with (a-c) $q = 0.3$ (top row) and (d-f) $q = 0.5$ (bottom row). The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

(s, ψ) solving these equations implies $x = s + \psi$ satisfying Eq.(1). Substituting Eq.(3) into Eq.(1), we obtain

$$\ddot{s} + d\dot{s} + sF_0(t) + B\beta F_1(s, \psi) + C\gamma F_2(s, \psi) = f \cos \omega t. \quad (4)$$

$$\ddot{\psi} + d\dot{\psi} + \psi F_0(t) + B\beta F_3(s, \psi) + C\gamma F_4(s, \psi) = g \cos \Omega t, \quad (5)$$

where

$$F_0(t) = -A\omega_0^2(1 + q \cos \omega_p t),$$

$$F_1(s, \psi) = s^3 + 3s^2 \langle \psi \rangle + 3s \langle \psi^2 \rangle + \langle \psi^3 \rangle,$$

$$F_2(s, \psi) = s^5 + 5s^4 \langle \psi \rangle + 5s \langle \psi^4 \rangle + 10s^3 \langle \psi^2 \rangle + 10s^2 \langle \psi^3 \rangle + \langle \psi^5 \rangle, \quad (6)$$

$$F_3(s, \psi) = (\psi^3 - \langle \psi \rangle^3) + 3s^2(\psi - \langle \psi \rangle) + 3s(\psi^2 - \langle \psi \rangle^2), \quad (7)$$

$$F_4(s, \psi) = (\psi^5 - \langle \psi \rangle^5) + 5s^4(\psi - \langle \psi \rangle) + 5s(\psi^4 - \langle \psi \rangle^4) + 10s^3(\psi^2 - \langle \psi \rangle^2) + 10s^2(\psi^3 - \langle \psi \rangle^3). \quad (8)$$

The solution of Eq.(5) is of the form is

$$\ddot{\psi} + d\dot{\psi} = gU \cos(\Omega t + \phi) + gV [\cos(\chi t + \alpha) + \cos(\xi t + \alpha)], \quad (9)$$

where χ, ξ are new frequencies and U, V are new amplitude factors, which are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= \Omega + \omega_p, & \xi &= \Omega - \omega_p, \\ U &= [(\Omega^2 - A\omega_0^2)^2 + d^2\Omega^2]^{1/2} / \Omega(\Omega^2 + d^2)^{1/2}, \\ V &= \frac{qR}{2}; & R &= \frac{A\omega_0^2}{\Omega\sqrt{\Omega^2 + d^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

FIG. 5. The theoretical response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_1 with (a) $d = 0.1$ (top figure) and (b) $d = 0.2$ (bottom figure). The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, q = 0.1, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

Also, the new phase terms are

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{d}{\Omega} \right], \quad \phi = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{d\Omega}{\Omega^2 - A\omega_0^2} \right]. \quad (10)$$

The solution of Eq.(11) evaluates with three forcing terms and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(t) = & \frac{g}{\mu_1} \cos(\Omega t + \phi + \theta) + \frac{g}{\mu_2} \cos(\chi t + \alpha + \delta) \\ & + \frac{g}{\mu_3} \cos(\xi t + \alpha + \nu). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Substituting the first and second derivatives of $\psi(t)$ in Eq.(11) and equating the coefficients, we

get the additional amplitudes are

$$\mu_1 = \frac{\Omega^2(\Omega^2 + d^2)}{\sqrt{(\Omega^2 - A\omega_0^2)^2 + \Omega^2 d^2}}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mu_2 = \frac{2\chi\Omega}{qA\omega_0^2} [(\chi^2 + d^2)(\Omega^2 + d^2)]^{1/2}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mu_3 = \frac{2\xi\Omega}{qA\omega_0^2} [(\xi^2 + d^2)(\Omega^2 + d^2)]^{1/2}, \quad (14)$$

and phase terms are

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}(d/\Omega), \quad (15)$$

$$\delta = \tan^{-1}(d/\chi), \quad (16)$$

$$\nu = \tan^{-1}(d/\xi). \quad (17)$$

The high-frequency periodic functions in the form of $\psi(t)$ in Eq. (13) confirm that the average of $\psi(t)$ over a complete time period is zero, as stated in Eq. (3). Equations (14-16) implies that, due to the largeness of Ω , the magnitudes of the μ_i (where $i = 1, 2, 3$) are of the order of Ω^2 . Consequently, this results in the small amplitude of the high-frequency term in Eq. (13), justifying the self-consistent technique developed to derive Eq. (11) above. From Eq. (11), it follows that the averages of $\psi(t)$ are $\langle \psi \rangle = \langle \psi^3 \rangle = \langle \psi^5 \rangle = 0$, $\langle \psi^2(t) \rangle = \frac{g^2}{2} \sum \frac{1}{\mu_i^2}$, and $\langle \psi^4(t) \rangle = \frac{3}{8} g^4 \sum \frac{1}{\mu_i^4}$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$. Thus, Eq. (4) for the slow motion becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{s} + d\dot{s} + (\bar{\omega}^2 - A\omega_0^2 q \cos \omega_p t) s \\ + [(B\beta + 10C\gamma \langle \psi^2 \rangle) s^3 + C\gamma s^5] = f \cos \omega t, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\omega}^2(g) = & 3\beta' \langle \psi^2 \rangle + 5C\gamma \langle \psi^4 \rangle - A\omega_0^2 \\ = & \frac{3}{2} g^2 \beta' \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^2} + \frac{15}{8} C\gamma g^4 \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^4} - A\omega_0^2, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\beta' = B\beta + 10C\gamma \langle \psi^2 \rangle = B\beta + 5C\gamma g^2 \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^2}. \quad (20)$$

FIG. 6. Bifurcation diagrams as a function of g showing (a) a periodic orbit, chaotic orbit and reversed period-doubling bifurcation for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$. (b) The magnification of Fig.6(a). (c-d) The deformation of bifurcation structure in 6(a) when $\alpha_1 = 1.0$ and 2.0 . The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, q = 0.1, d = 0.3, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

From Eq.(20), we defined the time dependent effective frequency as

$$\omega_{eff}(t) = \sqrt{\bar{\omega}^2 - A\omega_0^2 q \cos \omega_p t}, \quad (21)$$

and the effective potential is given by

$$V_{eff}(s, t) = \frac{1}{2}\omega_{eff}^2(t)s^2 + \frac{1}{4}\beta' s^4 + \frac{1}{6}C\gamma s^6. \quad (22)$$

In Eq. (20), the term $(\bar{\omega}^2 - A\omega_0^2 q \cos \omega_p t) > 0$. Consequently, the effective equation describes a forced quintic oscillator within an oscillatory monostable potential. This transition from bistable to monostable is influenced by the high-frequency forcing $g \cos \Omega t$ term.

3.2. The flow equations

To make further progress, we derive the amplitude and phase flow equations from Eq. (20), substituting the parametric frequency (ω_p) with the slow drive frequency (ω), i.e., $\omega = \omega_p$. The flow equations are obtained using standard perturbation techniques, such as the method of averaging. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the nonlinear response when the oscillator's natural frequency (ω_0) aligns with the low-frequency drive (ω), known as the primary resonance. This is achieved by finely tuning ω to be close to the frequency $\bar{\omega}$ specified in Eq. (21). To facilitate this exploration, we introduce

FIG. 7. Response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_2 with (a) $\Omega = 12$ and $\Omega = 15$. The theoretical and numerical values of $a_0(\omega)$ are represented by continuous lines and painted circles. The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, q = 0.1, f = 0.05$ and $\omega = \omega_p = 1.0$.

a detuning parameter $\bar{\sigma}$, expressing ω as $\bar{\omega} + \epsilon\bar{\sigma}$, where ϵ serves as a perturbation parameter. To

apply the perturbation technique, Eq. (20) is rearranged as follows:

$$\ddot{s} + \bar{\omega}^2 s = \epsilon [-d\dot{s} + A\omega_0^2 q(\cos \omega t)s - \beta' s^3 - C\gamma s^5 + f \cos \omega t]. \quad (23)$$

Introducing the rescaled the parameters $\frac{\bar{\omega}^2}{\omega^2} = 1 - \epsilon\sigma$, $\Gamma = \frac{d}{\omega^2}$, $\Lambda = \frac{\beta'}{\omega^2}$, $\alpha = \frac{C\gamma}{\omega^2}$, $m = f/\omega^2$ and $K = \frac{A\omega_0}{\omega^2}$. Calculations become simpler on introducing a dimensionless time $\tau = \omega t$ and rewriting Eq. (25) as

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{s} + s &= \epsilon [-\Gamma\dot{s} + K \cos \tau s + \Lambda s^3 + \alpha s^5 + f \cos \tau + \sigma s]. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The flow equations can be arrived at through the method of averaging, the details of which have described in refs.[28]. For using the method of averaging we can write $s = u \cos \omega t - v \sin \omega t$

with $u(t) = a(t) \cos \theta(t)$ and $v(t) = a(t) \sin \theta(t)$ and proceeding as usual [28], we arrive at the amplitude and phase flow equations

$$\dot{a} = -\omega [\Gamma a + m \sin \theta], \quad (25)$$

and

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega \left[-\sigma + \frac{3}{4}\Lambda a^2 + \frac{5}{8}\alpha a^4 - \frac{m}{a} \cos \theta \right]. \quad (26)$$

For the fixed points (a_0, θ_0) of this dynamical system, we obtain the following expression in the modified detuning parameter σ as,

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{3}{4}\Lambda a_0^2 + \frac{5}{8}\alpha a_0^4 \right] \pm \sqrt{\frac{m^2}{a_0^2} - \Gamma^2}. \quad (27)$$

FIG. 8. Response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_2 with (a) $\omega = \omega_p = 1.5$ and $\omega = \omega_p = 2.0$. The theoretical and numerical values of $a_0(\omega)$ are represented by continuous lines and painted circles. The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, q = 0.1, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12.0$.

Now, we substitute Eq. (29) in the modified detuning parameter, then $\bar{\omega}^2 = \omega^2 - \epsilon\omega^2\sigma$, i.e., $\frac{\bar{\omega}^2}{\omega^2} = 1 - \epsilon\sigma$,

$$\bar{\omega}^2 = \omega^2 - \epsilon \left\{ \left[\frac{3\beta'a_0^2}{4} + \frac{5}{8}C\gamma a_0^4 \right] \pm \sqrt{\frac{f^2}{a_0^2} - d^2\omega^2} \right\}. \quad (28)$$

Substituting the value of β' in Eq. (22), we get

$$\bar{\omega}^2 = \frac{3}{2}g^2\beta \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^2} + \frac{75}{8}\gamma g^4 \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^4} - \omega_0^2. \quad (29)$$

Now combining the Eqs. (21) and (31), we get

$$\frac{3}{2}g^2\beta' \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^2} + \frac{15}{8}C\gamma g^4 \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\mu_i^4} = (\omega^2 + A\omega_0^2) - \epsilon \left\{ \left[\frac{3\beta'a_0^2}{4} + \frac{5}{8}C\gamma a_0^4 \right] \pm \sqrt{\frac{f^2}{a_0^2} - d^2\omega^2} \right\}. \quad (30)$$

In Eq. (32), a functional relationship is established between the nonlinear response amplitude (a_0) and the strength of the high-frequency drive (g). This relationship reveals that

the high-frequency forcing serves to amplify the resonant response to the low-frequency drive (ω). Subsequent sections delve into the influence of depth and location of a minimum of the double-well potential on the vibrational resonance in a parametrically driven quintic oscillator.

4. Role of depth of the potential wells on vibrational resonance

In this section, we consider the system PS1, i.e. the system with the parameters $A = B = C = \alpha_1$. The potential for resonance occurrence, along with the values of the parameter at which resonance occurs, can be investigated by varying a control parameter. This exploration is facilitated by the theoretical expression of $a_0(\omega)$ (Eq. 32). To validate and compare with the theoretical response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ given by Eq. (32), we calculate $a_0(\omega)$ from the numerical solution of Eq. (1). We initiate this process by expressing Eq. (1) as a set of coupled first-order autonomous ordinary differential equations (ODEs), given in

FIG. 9. The theoretical response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_2 with (a) $q = 0.3$ and (b) $q = 0.5$. The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0$, $\beta = 1.0$, $\gamma = 1.0$, $d = 0.3$, $\omega = \omega_p = 1.0$, $f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

the following form:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = y, \quad (31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dy}{dt} = & -dx + A\omega_0^2(1 + q \cos \omega_p t)x - B\beta x^3 \\ & - C\gamma x^5 + f \cos \omega t + g \cos \Omega t. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

To numerically analyze Eq. (1), we utilize the fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme with time step sizes of $\Delta t = 0.001$. The initial conditions are set as $x(0) = 1$ and $y(0) = 1$, and the total simulation time is $t = 4000$, with the exclusion of the first 100 iterates to account for transients. The following parameters were fixed throughout the paper $\omega_0^2 = 1$, $\beta = 1.0$, $\gamma = 1.0$, $\omega = \omega_p$ and $f = 0.05$. We compare the numerically obtained $a_0(\omega)$ values with their corresponding analytical values by superimposing response curves for various system parameters. The response amplitudes $a_0(\omega)$ at the output signal frequency are denoted as $a_0(\omega)_s$ and $a_0(\omega)_c$, defined as follows:

$$a_0(\omega) = \frac{\sqrt{a_0(\omega)_s^2 + a_0(\omega)_c^2}}{f}, \quad (33)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_0(\omega)_s &= \frac{2}{nT} \int_0^{nT} x(t) \sin \omega t dt, \\ a_0(\omega)_c &= \frac{2}{nT} \int_0^{nT} x(t) \cos \omega t dt \end{aligned}$$

with $T = 2\pi/\omega$ and $n = 200$.

First we examine the effect of depth of the wells (α_1) on vibrational resonance by varying the frequency of the high-frequency force (Ω) both analytically and numerically.

Figure 2(a) depicts the plot of $a_0(\omega)$ for three values of α_1 ($=0.75, 1.0, 2.0$), computed from Eq. (32) and superimposed with the corresponding numerical curves obtained from Eq. (35) using Eq. (1) for comparison. The continuous curves represent the theoretically calculated $a_0(\omega)$ from Eq. (24), while the painted circles represent numerically computed Q from Eq. (35). It is evident that the theoretical and numerical results are in close agreement.

In Fig. 2(a), for $\Omega = 12$ at $g = 0$, the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ is observed at $a_0(\omega) = 0.42$ for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$, $a_0(\omega) = 0.32$ for $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, and $a_0(\omega) = 0.22$ for $\alpha_1 = 2.0$. As

FIG. 10. The response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of α_2 with (a) $d = 0.1$ and (b) $d = 0.2$. The theoretical and numerical values of $a_0(\omega)$ are represented by continuous lines and painted circles. The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, q = 0.1, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

g increases from zero, the response amplitude gradually increases and reaches its maximum value. Further increases in the g values result in a decrease in the peak of the curves. A similar behavior is observed for $\Omega = 15$ as well. For all values of α_1 , double resonance occurs. For $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0, 2.0$, the first and second resonances occur at $(46.67, 134.59), (57.88, 119.29)$, and $(75.41, 107.60)$, respectively. The peaks of the first resonance decrease as α_1 increases, but the peaks of the second resonance remain unaltered, as clearly seen in Fig. 2(a). However, the position

of the resonance peaks shifts further away from the origin as the value of α_1 increases. For $\Omega = 15$, the response curves for three values of α_1 are shown in Fig. 2(b). Once again, double resonances occur for all values of α_1 . For $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0, 2.0$, the first and second resonances occur at $(69.08, 196.01), (89.58, 185.35)$, and $(115.69, 167.74)$, respectively. From Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), it is evident that resonances occur earlier for $\Omega = 12$ compared to $\Omega = 15$. Additionally, the positions of the first and second resonances shift towards the higher amplitude region as the value of Ω increases.

To examine the effect of α_1 on vibrational resonance by varying the frequency of the low-frequency force (ω) of the system, we demonstrate the dependence of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ on g for two values of $\omega = \omega_p = 1.5, 2.0$ with $\Omega = 12$ in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b). In Fig. 3(a), at $\omega = 1.5$ and $g = 0$, the response amplitude is observed at $a_0(\omega) = 1.1$ for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$, $a_0(\omega) = 0.92$ for $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, and $a_0(\omega) = 0.34$ for $\alpha_1 = 2.0$. With further increases in g values, the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ increases. Single resonance is observed for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$ and 1.0 , whereas double resonance occurs for $\alpha_1 = 2.0$, as evident in Fig. 3(a). The response curves for $\omega = 2.0$ are depicted in Fig. 3(b) for three values of $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0, 2.0$ with $\Omega = 12$. Again, single resonance is observed for 0.75 and 1.0 , while double resonance occurs for $\alpha_1 = 2.0$. From Fig. 3(a), it is observed that at $g = 0$ with $\omega = 1.5$, the maximum amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ occurs for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$, and the amplitude decreases as α_1 increases. However, for $\omega = 2.0$, the situation is reversed. The maximum of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ occurs for $\alpha_1 = 2.0$, and the amplitude decreases as α_1 decreases.

The influence of the depth of the potential wells (α_1) on VR by varying the amplitude of the parametric excitation (q) is shown in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4, we have plotted the theoretical values of $a_0(\omega)$ against g for $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0, 2.0$ with $q = 0.3$ and $q = 0.5$. The other parameter values are fixed at $\omega = \omega_p = 1.0, \Omega = 12$, and $d = 0.3$. The response curves for $q = 0.3$ are shown in Figs. 4(a-c) (top row). For $\alpha_1 = 0.75$, double resonance

FIG. 11. Bifurcation diagrams as a function of g for values of $\alpha_2 = 0.75, 1.3, 1.6, 2.0$ with $q = 0.3$. Periodic orbits occur for all values of α_2 . The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

occurs; three resonances occur for $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, and six resonances occur for $\alpha_1 = 2.0$. That is, the number of resonances increases as the depth of the well (α_1) increases, as clearly shown in Fig. 4(a-c). The theoretical response curves for $q = 0.5$ are shown in Fig. 4(d-f) (bottom row). Multiple resonances occur for all the values of α_1 . In Fig. 4, it is observed that as the amplitude of the parametric excitation q increases, the number of resonances also increases. Next, we consider the effect of the depth of the potential wells (α_1) on VR by varying the damping strength d of the system. Figure 5 shows the theoretical response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ as a function of g for three values of $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0, 2.0$ with $d = 0.1$ and $d = 0.2$. For $d = 0.1$, triple resonance occurs for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$,

whereas double resonances occur for $\alpha_1 = 1.0$ and 2.0 . These results are presented in Fig. 5(a). When we increase the value of damping strength (d) (i.e., for $d = 0.2$), double resonances occur for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$, and triple resonances occur for $\alpha_1 = 1.0$ and 2.0 , as clearly seen in Fig. 5(b). From figures 5(a) and 5(b), we clearly observe that for $d = 0.1$, initially the resonances occur with smaller amplitude, whereas for $d = 0.2$, the situation is reversed; initially, the resonance occurs with higher amplitude, as clearly seen in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b).

The actual motion of Eq. (1) is studied for the parametric choices $\omega_0^2 = 1, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, \Omega = 12, d = 0.3, f = 0.05$, and $\alpha_1 = 0.75, 1.0, 2.0$. Figure 6 shows the bifurcation

FIG. 12. Bifurcation diagrams as a function of g for values of $\alpha_2 = 0.75, 1.3, 1.6, 2.0$ with $q = 0.5$. Periodic and chaotic orbits occur as increases the values of α_2 . The other parameters values are fixed at $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, f = 0.05$ and $\Omega = 12$.

diagram of Eq. (1). We restricted our analysis to the range $0 < g < 200$. For $\alpha_1 = 0.75$, the period- T solution is found in the range $0 < g < 78.33$, and chaotic motion and other periodic orbits are found for $g \in [78.33, 200]$. This is shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b). Figure 6(b) is the magnification of Fig. 6(a). For $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, the period- $2T$ orbit is found in the small range $72.06 < g < 78.84$, and in the remaining range, a period- T orbit is found, as clearly shown in Fig. 6(c). For $\alpha_1 = 2.0$, no chaotic motion appears; that is, the system shows fully periodic behavior, which is clearly shown in Fig. 6(d).

5. Role of location of minima of the potential on vibrational resonance

Similarly, the impact of the potential wells on Vibrational Resonance (VR) in the PS2 system can be explored. For PS2 with $A = 1/\alpha_2^2, B = 1/\alpha_2^4$, and $A = 1/\alpha_2^6$, as α_2 increases, the location of the two minima of $V(x)$ move away from the origin in the opposite direction. In other words, the distance between a minimum and the local maximum $x_1^* = 0$ of the potential increases with an increase in α_2 . We initiate our examination of the resonance phenomenon in the PS2 system by considering the role of the location of minima of the potential (α_2), as presented in Fig. 7 for

both theoretical $a_0(\omega)$ computed from Eq. (32) and numerical $a_0(\omega)$ obtained from Eq. (35) using Eq. (1). The analysis is restricted within the range $0 < g < 300$.

Figs. 7(a-b) depict the superimposed response curves illustrating the dependence of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ on the amplitude of the high-frequency signal for three values of $\alpha_2 = (0.75, 1.3, 1.6)$ with $\Omega = 12$ and 15 . The continuous lines represent the response curves of theoretically computed $a_0(\omega)$ values, while the painted circles represent corresponding numerical values. The other parameter values are $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, q = 0.1$, and $f = 0.05$. The system is driven into a resonant state by varying the amplitude of the fast signal g , and the number of peaks is dictated by the location of the minima of the potential wells (α_2). Here we observe that the VR effect can be induced in the system by increasing the values of α_2 . Moreover, there is close agreement between the theoretical and numerical results.

In Fig. 7(a), for $\Omega = 12$, triple resonances occur for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$ within the range $0 < g < 200$ with smaller response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$. The motion becomes unbounded when $g > 200$. For $\alpha_2 = 1.3$ and 1.6 , double resonances occur with higher amplitudes. It is observed from Fig. 7(a) that the peaks of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ and the resonance intervals increase as α_2 increases. However, in Fig. 7(b) for $\Omega = 15$, triple resonances occur for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$, two resonances occur for $\alpha_2 = 1.3$, and only one resonance occurs for $\alpha_2 = 1.6$ in the range $0 < g < 300$. Here, once again, the width and peaks of the response curves increase as α_2 increases. The difference in the effect of the distance of $x_{2,3}^*$ from the origin over the depth of the potential wells can be seen by comparing Figure 7 with Figure 2. In PS1, as α_1 increases, the peaks of the amplitude curves decrease. However, in PS2, as α_2 increases, the peaks of the curves also increase. In PS2, the separation between the two resonances increases with an increase in α_2 . The converse effect is noticed in the PS1 system.

By making a comparison between PS1 and PS2, we can conclude that the location parameter α_2 affects not only the length of the non-resonance interval but also the position of the intervals, and the depth parameter α_1 only impacts the former.

To examine the effect of α_2 on the system's response, we illustrate the dependence of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ on the amplitude of the fast signal g for three values of $\alpha_2 = 0.75, 1.3, 1.6$ with $\omega = 1.5$ and 2.0 in Fig. 8(a-b). The impact of ω on the response curves is evident. The analysis is restricted within the range $0 < g < 300$. For $\omega = 1.5$, single resonance occurs for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$ and 1.6 , but two resonances occur for $\alpha_2 = 1.3$. For $\omega = 2.0$, single resonance occurs for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$ and 1.3 , whereas no resonance occurs for $\alpha_2 = 1.6$. In contrast, in system PS1, double resonance occurs for $\alpha_1 = 1.6$, and single resonance occurs for $\alpha_1 = 0.75$ and 1.3 (Fig. 3). In Fig. 8(a-b), it is clearly observed that as ω increases, the peak positions of the response curves move away from the origin.

Next, we investigate the effect of α_2 on Vibrational Resonance (VR) by varying the strength of the parametric excitation (q). We begin by examining the change in the system's dynamics as the amplitude of the fast signal g is varied for three values of $\alpha_2 = 0.5, 1.3, 1.6$ with $q = 0.3$. The results are presented in Fig. 9(a). For $q = 0.3$, as α_1 and α_2 increase, in PS1, the number of resonances increases when α_1 increases; in PS2, two resonances appear initially, followed by four and three resonances. For $q = 0.5$, both systems PS1 and PS2 show multiple resonances, which is clearly shown in Fig. 4(d-f) and Fig. 9(b). Also, the separation between the resonances increases with an increase in α_2 . However, the converse effect is noticed in PS1.

The effect of damping strength d is illustrated in Fig. 10. Figure 10(a) presents the evolution of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ versus g for three values of $\alpha_2 = 0.75, 1.3, 1.6$ with $d = 0.1$. This manifests in the response peak becoming higher, and the position of the peak becomes farther from the origin as α_2 increases from 0.75 to 1.6 . This shows that when the

distance between the neighboring wells is larger, the particle can complete the jump better and initiate a satisfactory output response in the Vibrational Resonance (VR) system. Conversely, with the increase of the depth parameter α_1 , the peak of the response amplitude $a_0(\omega)$ in PS1 decreases, and the position of the peak gradually moves toward the origin (Fig. 5). The response curves for $d = 0.2$ are presented in Fig. 10(b). In Fig. 10(a) for $d = 0.1$, double resonances occur for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$ and 1.3 , whereas triple resonances occur for $\alpha_2 = 1.6$. Conversely, for $d = 0.2$, double resonances occur for all the values of α_2 . Also, the distance between the neighboring wells is larger for $d = 0.2$ than $d = 0.1$.

To complete the discussions, we present in Figures 11 and 12 the bifurcation diagrams of the PS2 system for $q = 0.1$ and $q = 0.5$, both as functions of the parameter g , while the other parameters are fixed as $\omega_0^2 = 1.0, \omega = \omega_p = 1.0, \beta = 1.0, \gamma = 1.0, d = 0.3, \Omega = 12$, and $f = 0.05$. The bifurcation diagram of $q = 0.3$ for four values of α_2 is shown in Fig. 11. For all the values of α_2 , the system PS2 shows only a periodic behavior. The motion is unbounded when $g > 44.5$ for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$, $g > 114.85$ for $\alpha_2 = 1.3$, and $\alpha_2 > 156.72$ for $\alpha_2 = 1.6$. The bifurcation diagram of $q = 0.5$ for four values of α_2 is shown in Fig. 12. The PS2 shows completely periodic behavior for $\alpha_2 = 0.75$. When we increase the values of α_2 from 0.75 , the PS2 system shows chaotic orbit, period-doubling, periodic bubble, and reverse periodic orbit. These results are clearly seen in Figs. 12(b-d).

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, we systematically investigated the impact of well depth and the distance between neighboring wells in a parametrically

driven double-well quintic oscillator. The oscillator, in addition to parametric excitation, experienced two additional driving forces—one with a low frequency (ω) equal to the parametric drive frequency (ω_p) and another with a much higher frequency (Ω). Applying the flow equation approach and the method of averages perturbation technique, we derived flow equations for both amplitude and phase to describe the slow dynamics of the system. This analytical approach allowed us to establish a functional relationship between the nonlinear response amplitude ($a_0(\omega)$) and the strength of the high-frequency drive (g). Our findings reveal the significant roles played by the depth of potential wells and the location of minima in influencing vibrational resonance. In contrast to conventional studies that focus solely on the strength of the fast drive as a control parameter for examining response and bifurcation behaviors, we extended our analysis to consider the fast frequency (Ω), parametric strength (q), and damping strength (d) as additional control parameters. Notably, these parameters can be manipulated to either suppress or induce resonance, providing a means to modulate resonance peaks and exert control over their occurrence in both PS1 and PS2 systems. Through a comparative analysis of PS1 and PS2, we concluded that the location parameter α_2 not only affects the length of the non-resonance intervals but also the position of the intervals and the depth parameter α_1 impacts the former.

Future research on the analysis of the effect of depth and location of minimum potential wells on vibrational resonance in nonlinearly damped systems and parametrically driven systems with triple-well potentials holds the potential to provide additional insights into the occurrence of vibrational resonance.

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